

Mantodea

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Mantodea: *Amorphoscelidae*

HW

Plesiomorphic !! for blattoids

Mantodea: Chaetussidae: *Chaetussa*

FW

HW Chaetussidae: *Chaetussa*

Zool. Inst. Russian Acad. Sci St. Petersburg J 1995

Empusidae:
Empusa tricornis

FW

HW Empusidae: *Empusa tricornis*

HW Mantodea: family unknown

Borneo

FW

Mantodea: Family?

Ecuador

CAL. Academy
San Francisco
very colourful

ScP

R & MA

MP

CuA

CuP

AA 1+2

AA 3+4
8

AP

HW Mantodea: Family? Ecuador

CAL Academy,
San Francisco

very colourful

Kameron

Hymenopodidae: *Pseudocreobotra ocellata*

(Beauvois)

FW Hymenoptera: *Pseudocreobotra ocellata*

HW Hymenopodidae: *Pseudocreobotra ocellata*

HW Hymenopodidae

Ecuador

Cal. Acad., San Francisco
Coll. Ross

FW Hymenopodidae

Ecuador

light brown, mottled
Cup reduced

CAL Acad. Sci., San Francisco, coll. Ross

Mantodea: Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.

HW Mantidae: Choeradodinae: *Choeradois*

SYNAPOMORPHY —
 anal lobe starts at anal fold ! as also in Heini and Endo !
 But in Plecoptera and Orthoptera it starts at claval line (symplexis!!)

FW Mantidae: *Choeradodis* sp.

Species differences in PR Sc and PR R???

Sorry...

overhang

precostal strip

FW Mantidae: Mantinae: *Hierodula atricoxis*

Ecuador

Mantodea: Mantidae: *Hierodula atricoxis* Ecuador

Mantodea: Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.
(plesio family)

Brazil Penn. Acad. Sci.

- ① Stem of M did not form
- ② MA fused with R
- ③ AA3+4 became part of remigium
- ④ AA1+2 reduced in HW

in HW
Anal lobe starts at anal fold

① (symplesiomorphy)
② (synapomorphy) shared by Blatto + Hemi + Endoptera

FW Mantidae: *Polypsilota aeruginea*

HW Mantodea: Mantidae: *Polypsilota aeruginosa*

Praying mantis

Tenodera costalis

New Caledonia

Polyspilota aeruginosa variagata

South Africa

Mantodea: *Tenodera costalis* New Caledonia

Wing flexing: left above right — more than 50% in Mantodea
 almost 100% in Blattodea

Mantidae: *Tenodera costalis*

New Caledonia

left wing above right wing:
 almost 100% Blattodea
 more than 50% of Mantodea

HW Mantodea: Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.

stem of Cu extremely short.
 FA and FJ connected by sclerotized trough

Mantodea: Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp. Brazil
 (plesio family!!)

Pennsylvania Acad. Sci.

Important plesio: shows that stem of M is absent !

FW Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.

FW Mantodea: Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.

Sistergroup of the rest of Mantodea; most primitive genitalia

FW Mantoididae: *Mantoida* sp.

Note that the cubital proxalare Cu-PR is not fused to the tergum (plesiomorphy)

Photidae: *Macromantis hyalina*

FW

- PC strip present!
- (Neoptera plesiomorphy)
- ScA ridge (blunt, blattoid)
- barely visible
- AA3+4 distinctly shifted toward AP
- BCu hidden under BAA

HW

- AA3+4 more separated from from AP fan than in Blattodea

FW Pyrgomantidae: *Tarachodes sanctus* S. Africa

